

TETR ARCHS

Transforming Data Reuse in Archaeology

D4.1 Data Capture Workflow Report

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Summary

This Deliverable 4.1, titled *Data Capture Workflow Workshop Report*, reports the results of Task 4.1 *Data Capture Workflows*. This task included undertaking a literature review and mapping and analysing existing data capture workflows associated with the project's four data acquisition technologies (airborne LiDAR, 3D scanning, digital drawing, photography) to inform Task 4.2 *Data Capture Experiment Design*. The discussion workshop aimed to map existing data capture workflows and analyse how they might be adapted to accommodate different user needs defined in WP2 and WP3, and different contexts (landscape, site, artefact). This report incorporates findings from the workshop, plus a wider scan of the extant literature.

Introduction

This Deliverable 4.1, titled *Data Capture Workflow Workshop Report*, reports the results of Task 4.1 Data Capture Workflows. This task included undertaking a literature review and mapping and analysing existing data capture workflows associated with the project's four data acquisition technologies to inform Task 4.2 Data Capture Experiment Design. The discussion workshop aimed to map existing data capture workflows and analyse how they might be adapted to accommodate different user needs defined in WP2 and WP3, and different contexts (landscape, site, artefact). This report incorporates findings from the workshop, plus a wider scan of the extant literature.

This deliverable focuses first on a literature review and summary of the current state of the art for data capture workflows, for four key data acquisition technologies, including:

- **Digital Photography in Archaeology**, with discussions on digital photographic workflows in on-site recording, photograph types, post-excavation analysis, and outputs.
- **3D Scanning in Archaeology**, with discussions on types of 3D models are employed in the field, image-based 3D modelling, laser scanning and structured light scanning.
- **Geographic Information Systems in Archaeology**, with discussions on types of GIS deployed by archaeologists, how archaeologists work with GIS, typical workflows for an intra-site GIS, outputs, and typical file formats used in Archaeological GIS.
- **LiDAR in Archaeology**, with discussions on raw data acquisition and processing, point cloud processing and derivation of products, archaeological interpretation, dissemination and archiving and workflow implementation.

Secondly, this deliverable documents the Data Capture Online Workshop held on 22 May 2023. The aim of the workshop was to explore how metadata generated via data capture workflows can be adapted to meet the storytelling needs of different audiences, including multi-disciplinary specialists, creative practitioners, memory institutions and their constituencies.

In attendance were invited speakers and specialists as well as project members from ZRC SAZU, MOLA (Museum of London Archaeology), University of York, University of Antwerp, and Lund University. The workshop consisted of two parts, including:

- presentations from different experts working in different contexts with storytelling, LiDAR, 3D scanning, mapping and photography;
- a panel discussion reflecting on the relationship between these data capture/structuring processes and storytelling.

The deliverable concludes with an implementation and reporting schedule, including plans for future collaboration with WP5.

Data capture workflows: state of the art

This section represents the literature review and analysis of the existing data capture workflows associated with the project's four data acquisition technologies (airborne LiDAR, 3D scanning, digital drawing, photography) set out in Task 4.1 *Data Capture Workflows* to inform Task 4.2 *Data Capture Experiment Design*.

Digital Photography

The history of photography in archaeology dates back to the mid-19th century, with the advent of early photographic techniques such as daguerreotypes and glass plate negatives. Archaeologists recognised early on the potential of photography for capturing and preserving detailed visual records of their work. As such, photography has played a crucial role in archaeology from the inception of the discipline, forming one of the three pillars of professional archaeological archives (alongside the written and graphical components). Photography provides a clear, comprehensive, and often evocative means to document and record archaeology at multiple scales, including excavations, artefacts, and archaeological sites, monuments, and landscapes.

Over time, as technology advanced, film photography became the dominant medium. Archaeologists embraced film cameras for their convenience, versatility, and ability to produce high-resolution images. However, film photography had limitations, including the need for physical film rolls, chemical processing, and storage. These factors often hindered immediate access to the photographs and made the archival process complex.

In the last couple of decades, the transition from film photography to digital photography has revolutionised archaeological documentation. Digital cameras offer numerous advantages, including instant feedback, easy image review, and the ability to capture a large number of images without the need for physical film. Digital photographs can be quickly transferred to computers or storage devices for processing, analysis, and archival purposes. This has significantly improved the efficiency of archaeological fieldwork and enhanced data management.

Moreover, digital photography allows for easy integration with other digital tools and technologies used in archaeology, such as Geographic Information Systems (GIS), photogrammetry, and 3D modelling. It enables the creation of interactive visual records and facilitates data sharing and collaboration among archaeologists worldwide.

The transition to digital photography has brought about increased accuracy, speed, accessibility, and versatility in archaeological documentation. It has transformed the way archaeological data is collected, analysed, stored, and shared, leading to more efficient and comprehensive research outcomes.

Digital Photographic Workflows in On-Site Recording

Digital photography plays a crucial role in any workflow in archaeology, which aims to document archaeological context stratigraphically, and their relationships within a site. Commonly there are various types of photographs that are integrated into the site archive and which may be required at different points, serving different purposes in the recording process. The incorporation of digital photography into the core site archive creates a visual record that supports the written and graphic archive, enhancing the understanding of the site and its depositional sequence, its features, and their interrelationships. The photographic records serve as a valuable reference for analysis, interpretation, as well as a pivotal medium for sharing findings with other researchers and the public (and are crucial to support publications at every level, along with presentations).

Typically, the workflow relating to digital photography in the documentation of a site begins in the pre-excavation planning stage of the excavation process, where decisions will be made about the specific types of photographs needed to document each feature and its associated details (see below). The precise nature, quantity, and deployment of different types of images will vary across different projects and organisations, which is critical to defining how digital images will be incorporated into the site archive from the outset.

It is important to assemble the necessary equipment, including a digital camera with appropriate settings and accessories and set up any additional tools, such as scales or reference objects, for size calibration and context. These settings should take into account best practice requirements for image quality and image file types (i.e., lossy versus lossless formats).

Protocols for documenting the photographs taken need to be established at this point (i.e., establishing a Photo Register (with core fields including, site code, relevant context/group/structure numbers, area/trench number, name of photographer, direction in which the image is facing and a short image description). It is important to ensure the camera's date and time settings are accurate for proper synchronisation with other documentation.

Photograph types

Types of photographs taken in the recording of an archaeological site include (but are not necessarily limited to):

Initial Photographs (pre-excavation and/or post-topsoil stripping):

These would typically include overview shots of the excavation area to establish the site's general context, as well as images of the surrounding landscape or visible features that provide geographical or spatial information. When a site is stripped of topsoil and initially cleaned it will ordinarily be photographed prior to any stratigraphic excavation.

Stratigraphic Unit Photography:

These would typically document each individual stratigraphic unit with detailed photographs before excavation. This would include overall shots of the feature from various angles to capture its shape, size, and relationship to nearby features as well as close-up images to highlight specific details, such as inclusions, lenses, or stratigraphic relationships. Images should always use a scale or reference object in the frame to provide a visual measurement for accurate scale representation. Sometimes it

is appropriate to capture images of the layers before and after their removal to maintain a comprehensive record (although in a single context recording system this is standard as the surface of every new stratigraphic unit is photographed as part of the system).

Stratigraphic Relationships:

This type of photograph may include more than one stratigraphic unit (i.e., in section) to evidence and record the stratigraphic relationships between different deposits. Ordinarily such photographs would use a scale, or less commonly a grid, as a reference system to ensure consistent photo points and accurate spatial documentation.

Group/Feature/Structure images:

Typically, these are another type of contextual photograph, which emphasises a series of stratigraphic units which might be linked (or grouped) functionally or spatially and possibly showing the relationship between the group/feature being excavated and its surrounding context. In the case of the latter, it would pan out to include adjacent features, layers, or structures that demonstrate their spatio-functional connections. This type of photograph may be duplicated so that the series might document any changes or disturbances caused by the excavation process.

Progression Photos (including working shots):

Throughout an excavation it is important to continuously document the excavation progress with regular photographs and working shots. These would capture images at significant stages, such as after each layer removal or feature cleaning, when an area is thought to be in phase, etc., with a view to recording notable findings, changes in the site, or observations made during the excavation. In particular, this type of image is critical for communicating aspect of the site for publication, presentation and online dissemination, as they tend to be more interesting to non-archaeologists and people less familiar with the sites (of particular value here are those images with people in them, i.e., working shots).

Archaeological Finds:

On site it is important to document all significant archaeological finds and artifacts discovered during the excavation. These might be photographed *in situ* prior to removal, to offer context for the find's location. But more importantly, typically each artefact would be photographed individually (probably off-site, perhaps post-excavation), ensuring clear and detailed images that capture its condition, context, and associated labels or markings. All images of both sorts should include a scale or reference object to indicate the artefact's size and should seek to capture images from multiple angles to showcase different sides and relevant details.

Post-excavation Analysis

Like any aspect of the primary archive, post-excavation the photographic archive needs to be checked, validated and cross referenced against the photographic register. Images should be filed systematically or ideally imported into suitable software for organising, annotating, and analysing the visual data. Appropriate metadata should be assigned, ideally including site code context/group/feature numbers, excavation unit references, and date and time information, as well as photographer ID. This will allow for the systematic comparison and cross-referencing of the photographs with other documentation, such as field notes or sketches, context sheets and plans.

Outputs

A digital photographic archive for an archaeological excavation typically includes various outputs in terms of file types and images. Some of the typical outputs are:

High-resolution digital photographs

These are the primary output of the photographic archive, capturing detailed visual records of excavations, artefacts, features, and archaeological contexts. These images are typically stored as high-resolution JPEG or TIFF files, ensuring high quality and compatibility.

Georeferenced photographs

In cases where photographs are associated with specific geographic locations within the excavation site, georeferencing is applied. Georeferenced images are often stored as JPEG or TIFF files with accompanying metadata that includes spatial coordinates.

Image catalogues and contact sheets.

These are compilations of thumbnail or low-resolution images that provide a quick overview of the entire photographic archive. Catalogues and contact sheets may be generated as PDF files or web galleries, allowing for easy browsing and reference.

Metadata files

These contain descriptive information about each photograph, including details such as date, location, subject, photographer, and any relevant contextual information. Metadata files are commonly stored in formats such as CSV (comma-separated values) or XML.

Image annotations

Annotations may be added to photographs to highlight specific features, provide explanations, or indicate measurements. These annotations can be stored as separate files, such as JPEG or PNG, with transparent backgrounds.

Derived products

The digital photographic archive may also generate derived products, such as orthophotos, photomosaics, or 3D models. These files can be in formats like JPEG, TIFF, or specialized 3D file formats (e.g., OBJ, PLY) depending on the specific output.

3D scanning

In the late 1990s, a series of experiments were conducted to examine the viability of incorporating 3D recording technology into archaeological fieldwork (Barceló et al. 2003; Losier et al. 2007). Laser scanning was introduced as part of various field investigations, and the results were often visualised in Geographic Information Systems (GIS) to provide a more comprehensive documentation of the investigative process. The utilisation of active sensors, such as laser scanning, to record archaeological contexts and features in high resolution was a novel concept. It expanded the realm

of 3D representations beyond mere reconstructions and started to be recognised as a sophisticated form of archaeological record, significantly influencing the knowledge production process.

Despite its effectiveness, this technology remains prohibitively expensive and requires a considerable level of expertise, limiting its widespread adoption. However, a significant turning point occurred with the emergence of 3D recording and visualisation techniques based on image-based 3D modelling. The introduction of this documentation method instigated a period of intense experimentation, where 3D models were generated and employed in the field as the primary means of documentation.

Image-based 3D modelling relied on more cost-effective equipment and employed an efficient, semi-automatic data processing workflow. This approach enables archaeologists to create highly accurate geometric 3D models with textures and dense point clouds using a set of digital images (Dell'Unto & Landeschi, 2022).

What type of 3D models are employed in the field?

3D spatial recording technologies enable the generation of various types of 3D data, each possessing distinct characteristics and capabilities. The most prevalent types of 3D models currently employed in archaeology can be categorised into surface, boundary, and volume representations (e.g., voxel and spatial decomposition models). These models have found extensive applications in supporting archaeological practices, and their utilisation has experienced remarkable growth over the past decade, permeating nearly every aspect of the discipline.

Surface representations encompass 3D objects consisting of points, lines, and surfaces, providing an external depiction of the object rather than its internal properties (Lock 2003:152; Hughes et al. 2014). Although these models have limitations in offering only a partial description of the represented object, their recent proliferation has sparked a phase of intensive experimentation. Consequently, new archaeological methodologies have emerged, progressively transforming archaeology into a collaborative and immersive discipline.

Boundary representations are characterised by a surface that maintains topological consistency. These models function as solids rather than mere shells (de Cambrey 1993:342), enabling the extraction of information such as volume, mass, and centre of gravity (Lock 2003:152). Archaeologists often employ boundary models to create virtual interpretations of artefacts and monuments or to analyse the stratigraphic relationships between encountered deposits during investigations.

Volume representations, such as voxel and spatial decomposition models, possess the ability to describe the internal space of an object. These models are particularly suitable for representing geological data (de Cambrey 1993:343). Their usage is highly significant in depicting datasets acquired through instruments capable of recording and assigning distinct values to the materials comprising the object (Dell'Unto & Landeschi, 2022)

Image-based 3D Modelling

This approach allows archaeologists to create accurate 3D models with textures and dense point clouds from a collection of digital images. First, the software calculates the camera parameters for each image, allowing it to be accurately positioned in space. It then detects and matches geometric

features visible in pairs of consecutive images. By estimating the positions of the pictures, a dense cloud is created, resulting in a geometrically accurate 3D model of the scene.

Figure 1: Illustration of the different steps used to create a 3D texture model.

The dense point cloud can be further utilised to create a high-resolution texture model. To achieve this, dense stereo reconstruction algorithms are employed. These algorithms analyse the cloud and generate a detailed geometric representation of the scene. This textured model can be scaled, georeferenced and serve as a valuable resource for extracting additional geometric information.

One significant advantage of these techniques is their increased accessibility. They can be implemented on standard desktop machines, making them more widely available to archaeologists. Overall, this method revolutionises the way archaeologists approach 3D modelling. It enables the creation of accurate and detailed representations from digital images, opening up new possibilities for research, analysis, and visualisation in archaeology.

Figure 2: Example of the intricate detail it is possible to capture using phase shift laser scanning.

Laser scanners

Phase shift laser scanning

Laser scanning technology has transformed the field of archaeology by facilitating accurate and detailed 3D data capture. One type of laser scanning that has gained prominence is phase shift laser scanning.

Phase shift laser scanning works by emitting a laser beam that scans the target object. The laser beam interacts with the surface, measuring the phase shift in the reflected light to produce a highly accurate 3D representation.

One of the key benefits of phase-shift laser scanning is its ability to capture intricate details accurately. It can detect even the most minor variations in surface geometry, capturing fine features, colours and subtle elevation

changes. This level of detail is crucial in archaeological research, allowing in-depth analysis and interpretation of significant monuments and sites.

In addition, phased laser scanning enables rapid data acquisition, making it efficient for capturing large archaeological environments. The scanner emits thousands of laser pulses per second, quickly capturing many data points. This data can then be processed to create comprehensive 3D models that provide a detailed record of the archaeological site or monument.

The use of phased laser scanning has revolutionised archaeological documentation and analysis. It offers archaeologists unprecedented accuracy, speed and detail, allowing them to capture and preserve archaeological sites and artefacts in their current state. This technology is key in advancing our understanding of the past, facilitating research, conservation and virtual reconstruction of historic environments.

Structured light scanner

A structured light scanner is a 3D scanning technology that uses projected light patterns to capture detailed geometric data of objects or environments. It is a non-contact method that is widely used in various industries due to its accuracy and efficiency.

In structured light scanning, a projector emits a series of known patterns, such as grids or stripes, onto the surface of the object being scanned. These patterns are projected from different angles, creating a distortion on the surface of the object. A camera or sensor captures the reflected or deformed patterns, and advanced algorithms analyse the distortions to calculate the 3D shape and geometry of the object.

One of the key benefits of structured light scanning is its ability to capture highly accurate and detailed 3D data. By projecting patterns with known characteristics, the scanner can accurately calculate the deformations and variations in the object's surface, creating intricate and precise 3D models.

One of the key advantages of structured light scanners is their ability to capture fine detail with exceptional accuracy. They can capture even the smallest intricacies and surface details, allowing archaeologists to analyse minute features of artefacts or architectural elements. This level of detail enhances our understanding of the past and facilitates identifying and interpreting cultural and historical significance.

Figure 3: A structured light scanner in use.

Geographic Information Systems in Archaeology

The use of Geographic Information Systems (GIS) in archaeology has significantly transformed the field by providing powerful tools for spatial analysis, data management, and visualisation. Over the years, GIS has increasingly become an integral part of archaeological research, allowing archaeologists to investigate and understand the spatial dimensions of past human activities.

The history of GIS in archaeology can be traced back to the 1970s when early adopters began exploring the potential of computer-based mapping and analysis (for a strong overview of this see for example Wheatley and Gillings 2002, or Conolly and Lake 2006). The introduction of digital technologies and advancements in computing capabilities (including related technologies such as Computer Aided Design), allowed researchers to digitise maps, integrate spatial data, and conduct basic spatial analyses.

In the 1980s, GIS applications in archaeology gained momentum as archaeologists recognised the value of spatial information for research and site management. They started using GIS to study settlement patterns, analyse landscape features, and model ancient environments. In the 1990s and early 2000s, GIS technology became more accessible and user-friendly, leading to its more widespread adoption in archaeology. Initially GIS research focused on large-scale analyses seeking to understand sites at an inter-site landscape or regional scale, but archaeologists quickly started incorporating GIS into fieldwork as a mechanism for handling the complex spatial data generated during excavation, by recording excavation data digitally and creating comprehensive intra-site GIS databases. This allowed them to analyse complex spatial relationships, visualise patterns, and address research questions related to site formation, social interactions, and cultural landscapes.

Today, GIS has become an increasingly indispensable tool in archaeological research. It is used for predictive modelling, site preservation planning, heritage management, and the integration of multiple datasets. With the advent of web-based GIS platforms, archaeologists can now collaborate, share data, and disseminate findings more easily, fostering interdisciplinary research and public engagement.

What types of GIS are deployed by archaeologists?

There are a range of ‘types’ of GIS that are currently readily available to the archaeological sector which may be more (or less) appropriate depending upon specific project requirements, available budget, technical expertise and software affordances and specific research objectives. Notably these include:

Desktop GIS

Traditional desktop GIS software, such as ArcGIS and QGIS, is widely utilised by archaeologists. These software packages offer a comprehensive range of tools for data management, analysis, and visualisation. They allow archaeologists to create, edit, and analyse spatial data on their computers and are suitable for both fieldwork and post-processing tasks.

Web-based GIS

Web-based GIS platforms, such as ArcGIS Online and Mapbox, have gained popularity in recent years. These platforms enable archaeologists to create interactive web maps, story maps, share data online, and collaborate with colleagues remotely. Web-based GIS facilitates easy data access, visualisation, and public engagement.

Mobile GIS

Mobile GIS applications, designed for smartphones and tablets, provide archaeologists with the ability to collect and update spatial data directly in the field. These apps, like Collector for ArcGIS and Fulcrum, allow for real-time data capture, GPS tracking, and attribute recording, enhancing efficiency and accuracy during fieldwork.

3D GIS

Recently the emergence of three-dimensional GIS applications, such as ESRI's CityEngine or open-source tools like Blender, have offered potential for their use in archaeological research for reconstructing and visualising ancient landscapes, architectural features, and cultural heritage sites. 3D GIS is still an emergent field in archaeological analysis, but offers clear potential for archaeologists to create realistic virtual representations, conduct virtual reality simulations, and analyse spatial relationships in three dimensions.

Open-Source GIS

Although it is not strictly a technology in its own right, it is worth noting that open-source GIS software, such as QGIS and GRASS GIS, are freely available and provide cost-effective alternatives to commercial software. Archaeologists often use open-source GIS tools for data analysis, mapping, and customisation, as they offer flexibility and a supportive community.

Working with GIS in Archaeology

As noted above there are a variety of ways that GIS is commonly deployed with archaeological research in the field. Generally, their deployment would fall into two broad categories of scale, which can be linked to different granularities of data, typically: **inter-site** and **intra-site** GIS.

Inter-site GIS

This has traditionally been (and probably remains) the more common scale of operation and includes landscape or regional level mapping and spatial analyses, where the archaeological site or monument effectively forms the base level granularity. Inter-site GIS focuses on analysing and understanding relationships and patterns between multiple archaeological sites within a region or study area. It involves the integration and analysis of data collected from different sites to explore regional settlement patterns, cultural interactions, or landscape use. Inter-site GIS helps archaeologists identify similarities, differences, and connections between sites, contributing to broader interpretations of human activities across a larger spatial context.

Intra-site GIS

Intra-site GIS, on the other hand, concentrates on the analysis and visualisation of spatial data *within* a single archaeological site or excavation area. As such, the base level granularity is generally that of

the stratigraphic unit, feature or structure. It focuses on capturing and understanding the detailed relationships and patterns among features, stratigraphic units, artefacts, and other archaeological elements within the site. Intra-site GIS allows archaeologists to document, analyse, and interpret the spatial context and organisation of archaeological materials within a specific area. It aids in understanding site formation processes, activity areas, spatial relationships between features, and cultural practices within the site boundaries.

Functionality

At whichever scale one is operating, in simple terms, the core functions of an effective archaeological Geographic Information System (GIS) can be summarised as follows:

Data Management

An archaeological GIS helps manage a wide range spatial data related to archaeological sites, features, artefacts, and other relevant information. It allows for the organisation, storage, and retrieval of geospatial data in a structured and efficient manner.

Spatial Analysis

GIS enables archaeologists to conduct various spatial analyses to explore patterns, relationships, and distributions within archaeological datasets. It provides tools to measure distances, calculate areas, identify clusters, and perform overlay analyses to gain insights into the spatial aspects of archaeological phenomena.

Mapping and Visualisation

GIS facilitates the creation of maps and visual representations of archaeological data. It facilitates the display of excavation units, features, artefact distributions, and other archaeological information on maps, aiding in the visualisation and communication of spatial patterns and findings.

Contextualisation and Interpretation

Archaeological GIS helps contextualise archaeological features and artefacts within their broader spatial context. By incorporating data on topography, landscape, and other environmental factors, GIS supports the interpretation of how human activities were influenced by and interacted with their surroundings.

Site Documentation and Recording

GIS serves as a digital platform for the documentation and recording of archaeological sites. It enables the integration of diverse datasets, such as excavation plans, photographs, field notes, and artefact inventories, into a unified spatial framework, facilitating comprehensive site documentation.

Predictive Modelling

GIS can be used for predictive modelling in archaeology. By analysing known archaeological sites and associated environmental variables, GIS can help identify areas with a high potential for undiscovered archaeological remains, aiding in survey and prioritisation efforts.

Heritage Management

GIS contributes to heritage management by supporting the assessment, planning, and monitoring of archaeological sites. It assists in the identification of areas requiring protection, aids in site preservation planning, and facilitates the monitoring of potential threats or changes to archaeological sites over time.

Typical Workflows for an intra-site GIS

For the most part, TETRARCH's researchers have been interested in collection and knowledge creation at an intra-site scale; following is a typical workflow for such a system. This typically includes the following steps:

- Start by collecting all relevant data, including survey data, excavation plans, field notes, and digital photographs. Organise and digitise the data in a format compatible with GIS software. Ensure consistent attribute values and standardised naming conventions are used for easy data integration. Alternatively design a system to record these data in a born-digital format.
- Determine the appropriate coordinate system and projection for the site. Assign these parameters to ensure accurate spatial referencing of data.
- Import or create base maps that provide a spatial framework for the site, such as topographic maps or aerial/satellite imagery. If necessary, digitise or trace key features like contour lines, water bodies, roads, boundaries or vegetation to create background layers in the GIS.
- Identify or set out (using a Differential Geographic Positioning System, for example) known control points within or near the site, such as surveyed benchmarks or other georeferenced features. Use these control points to align the base maps with the chosen coordinate system.
- Create individual feature layers based on the archaeological elements being recorded, such as excavation units, structures, features, and artefacts. Digitise or import the existing spatial data for each layer, ensuring alignment with the base maps and coordinate system.
- Create attribute tables to store information like excavation unit numbers, stratigraphic relationships, artefact descriptions, and other relevant details. Where necessary relate and link attribute data to the corresponding features within the GIS.
- It may be possible to define spatial relationships between different feature layers based on archaeological interpretation. Use topological rules to establish relationships like stratigraphic layers, overlapping features, or spatial associations.
- It may be possible to georeference digital photographs by identifying common reference points between the images and the GIS layers. Assign spatial coordinates to accurately place the photographs within the site context.
- Use onboard GIS analytical tools for spatial analysis to investigate relationships, patterns, and distributions within the site. Visualise the data through thematic maps, such as density maps, distribution maps, or hotspot maps.

- Perform queries in the GIS to extract specific information or generate reports based on selected criteria. Create maps, figures, and diagrams to support reports, publications, or presentations.
- Regularly update and maintain the GIS database by incorporating new data and revisions. Implement a version control system to track changes and ensure data integrity. Document the workflow, data sources, procedures, and assumptions for transparency and reproducibility.

Outputs

Common outputs for an Archaeological GIS can include:

- Digital maps displaying archaeological features, excavation units, artefact distributions, and site boundaries.
- Thematic maps illustrating spatial patterns, densities, and relationships within the site or across a broader landscape.
- 3D visualisations and models of archaeological sites, structures, or artefacts.
- Spatial analysis results, such as proximity analysis, clustering, or viewshed analysis.
- Georeferenced photographs, allowing for the integration of visual documentation within the GIS.
- Attribute tables providing detailed information about archaeological features, artefacts, and excavation units.

Typical file formats used in Archaeological GIS outputs include:

- Shapefile (SHP): A widely used vector format that stores both geometry and attribute data.
- GeoJSON: A format for encoding geographic data using JavaScript Object Notation (JSON).
- Geodatabase (GDB): A proprietary format commonly used in ESRI's ArcGIS software.
- Keyhole Markup Language (KML): A format used for displaying geographic data in Google Earth.
- Portable Document Format (PDF): Used for sharing maps, reports, and other outputs in a non-editable format.
- Image formats such as JPEG or TIFF for georeferenced photographs or map exports.

Archaeological LiDAR

Airborne LiDAR is nowadays a widely accepted tool for archaeological prospection. Using a combination of perception and comprehension, archaeologists interpret enhanced visualisations of high-resolution raster elevation models that have been interpolated from processed airborne LiDAR data. The results have proven to be an excellent tool for detecting archaeological features

worldwide, especially in forested areas. More importantly, mapping of features makes it possible to develop a more profound understanding of the archaeological landscapes. In comparison to other fields, the use of airborne LiDAR-derived data in archaeology is specific in several ways. Therefore, an archaeology-specific airborne LiDAR data processing workflow from mission planning to archiving has been developed.

The first step towards documenting any scientific process is to define it. An archaeology-specific airborne LiDAR data processing workflow, from mission planning to archiving, has been presented in several studies (Table 1). The first introduction was by Crutchley (2010), and was aimed at archaeologists in general, not at LiDAR specialists. It remains one of the most complete overviews of the workflow, however, it leaves out some important steps, most notably about point cloud processing. Nevertheless, it was written with an in-depth knowledge of the process, and the text remains a useful starting point for newcomers to the field. The first scientific presentation of the workflow was written by Doneus and Briese (2011). It describes the entire process of archaeology-specific data acquisition in great detail, while Doneus and Kühteiber (2013) published chapters in a monograph providing a general overview of airborne LiDAR in archaeology. The first focused on archaeological interpretation and the latter on all other aspects of the workflow. Fernandez-Diaz et al. (2014) was the first to use the Mesoamerican data to illustrate the workflow. It is by far the most complete analysis of archaeology-specific raw data acquisition and processing. Until the sensor technology changes radically, this text will retain its importance. Štular and Lozić (2016) focused on point cloud data processing for a specific set of off-the-shelf general-purpose data. This study demonstrated that with archaeology-specific data processing, general purpose data which may have seemed to be of too low quality can be successfully used in archaeology. Grammer et al. (2017) focused on archaeological interpretation and were the first to point out the importance of data integration. Doneus et al. (2020) focus on presenting a specific ground point filtering method, but they present a concise yet refreshed overview of the entire workflow as well.

Despite terminological differences, the studies cited agree on the general workflow.

The following workflow is based on the recent article by Lozić and Štular (2021) which provided an up-to-date and comprehensive review of the workflow. It comprised all steps introduced in recent years, and established a consistent terminology.

Workflow

Raw data Acquisition and Processing (1.1–1.5)

Raw data acquisition and processing consists of five steps. It needs to be mentioned, that the proposed workflow might be biased towards Riegel sensors, due to the bias in existing archaeology-specific literature.

(1.1) Project planning is important to ensure that the airborne LiDAR survey is tailored to specific scientific research questions.

(1.2) System calibration ensures that the point density will adequately support the desired raster resolution. To achieve this, the requirements of the researcher, local flight conditions and aviation regulations, and the performance specifications of the aircraft must be taken into account to establish an appropriate flight plan and system configuration.

(1.3) During the data acquisition step, the project plan is followed, but the LiDAR operator often needs to make real-time adjustments to take account of the conditions encountered during the flight.

(1.4) The raw data collected—also referred to as the primary data—constitute a series of measurements of the time and intensities of the returned laser pulses. In the data registration step, these data are correlated with the navigation information from the Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS), the inertial measurement unit (IMU), and the surveyed ground control points (GCP) to calculate the geodetic position of each laser return.

(1.5) The primary objective of flight strip adjustment is to provide quality assurance and quality control for the geospatial end product by reducing or ultimately eliminating the discrepancies found in the overlap areas of the strips, thus creating a seamless product.

Point Cloud Processing and Derivation of the Products (2.1–2.5)

A note on terminology is appropriate at this point. As noted elsewhere, the term algorithm is used to refer to theory (e.g., academic articles) and filter to implementation (e.g., in software). The term filtering is used to describe the process of applying the filter to the data. The ground extraction filters are used to classify each point in the point cloud as either ground or nonground and no point is deleted (filtered). However, when the DTM is interpolated from the point cloud, only the points classified as the ground are used and the rest are omitted (filtered) from the process. In the past this led to a certain ambiguity in the terminology, especially concerning the term filter/filtering (e.g., “ground-point filtering” versus “ground-point classification”).

Point cloud processing and the derivation of results is set out in the next five steps.

(2.1) The calculated positions are stored as a point cloud, with each point containing X, Y and Z coordinates and additional attribute information such as GPS time, intensity, echo-width, and scanning angle. These are individual points in space that have no physical relationship to each other, but due to their density can be used to define features such as ground or buildings. These features are defined by point cloud processing. Arguably, the most important step is the automatic ground point classification, where each point is classified either as ground (terrain) or non-ground (off-terrain). This is a probabilistic rather than a deterministic process, and any classification includes false positives (ground points classified as non-ground) and false negatives (non-ground points classified as ground).

(2.2) Next, non-ground points are further classified by object type. While any object type classification is based directly on the results of ground point classification, there are various approaches to this step in archaeological practice. Approaches range from ignoring this step altogether (only DEM is used) to making it the primary goal of the analysis (non-ground objects are the focus). Because of this diversity, this step is considered to be separate. Of archaeological interest are primarily non-ground archaeological features (for example castle ruins), but also buildings and sometimes vegetation. Points classified as vegetation are rarely directly relevant for archaeological interpretation, but low vegetation density can be used both for planning ground assessments (areas with dense low vegetation can only be surveyed during the season of dormant vegetation, while other areas may be accessible all year round) and as one of the proxies for the accuracy of the final

model (for example non-ground features are more likely to be lost in areas with dense low vegetation, regardless of the density of ground points).

(2.3) Currently successful automatic filtering methods are ideally up to 96.29% accurate, but within archaeological sites under unfavourable conditions the accuracy can be as low as 37%. Features at the cliff edges and non-ground archaeological features in dense vegetation are particularly prone to errors (see below). In such cases, a manual reclassification of the point cloud is essential. It is carried out by viewing the vertical profile sections of the point cloud and thus identifying and reclassifying incorrectly classified points. The process consists of a series of discrete micro decisions made by the operator, who relies heavily on the experience and knowledge of local geomorphology, vegetation, and archaeological features. Sometimes, a field survey in selected small areas is required to provide sufficient context data. The whole process is time-consuming and is therefore typically limited to focus areas of high archaeological importance.

(2.4) Based on the classified point cloud, a digital raster model is interpolated. Interpolation is a process in which a grid of defined cell size is effectively draped over the point data. This means that the cells are derived from the original data and do not consist of the actual data points. The archaeology-specific digital raster model combines a digital terrain model (DTM, also known as digital elevation model, DEM, in US-centric usage) with off-terrain archaeological features and, for contextual information, modern buildings. Such an “archaeological digital elevation model” has been termed the digital feature model (DFM).

(2.5) Enhanced visualisations are then computed from the DFM. One of the most important distinctions separating archaeology-specific from general mapping workflows is that instead of one visualisation (usually analytical hillshading) several enhanced visualisations are created, for example, sky view factor, openness and difference from mean elevation. Often, a fusion of several visualisations is used (see below).

Archaeological Interpretation (3.1–3.5)

Only at this stage does the archaeological interpretation begin.

(3.1) Airborne LiDAR data become particularly valuable in combination with other relevant data sources, both pertaining to the past and present (for example, archaeological geodatabases, aerial photographs, historical maps, geological maps, and soil maps). This is because airborne LiDAR, in the same manner as aerial photography, indiscriminately records information derived from many causes and spanning many millennia. Additional data sources are used to isolate the archaeological evidence. Therefore, as a first step in archaeological interpretation, all available relevant data are integrated into a GIS environment. The activity can be as simple as connecting a Web Map Service or as complex as discovering, retrieving, scanning, georeferencing, and vectorising historical maps.

(3.2) Interpretative mapping is a desk-based archaeological process in which archaeological sites and features are identified, interpreted, and mapped. It is based on analysis of the enhanced visualisations and additional data sources engaged in a GIS environment. The method draws from the interpretation of aerial photography, but there are key differences: the LiDAR data are born geocoded, the observer-oriented biases are negligible, and the features are recognised solely by their surface morphology. As a consequence, both the workflow and the results are specific to airborne LiDAR data.

The aim of interpretative mapping is to create a geodatabase containing archaeological features mapped as points, polylines, or polygons with associated feature-specific metadata. The geometry type depends on the type of project. For example, in a regional analysis that focuses on mapping previously unknown sites, an entire hillfort is mapped as a point. A similar hillfort, if it is a focus of an intra-site analysis, is mapped using a series of polygons and polylines. At a medium scale, for example, a cairnfield can be mapped either as points for ground assessment and dissemination or as polygons for a detailed morphological study. This is also reflected in the effort required to map a set area. A very rough estimate ranges from 19 km²/person/day for a regional project, 1 km²/person/day for a medium scale project (experience in the MALiAp project) or two days (0.02 km²/person/day) for an in-depth analysis of a complex site. In addition to the archaeological features, the so-called negative zones must also be mapped. Those are areas where no archaeological information can be obtained with airborne LiDAR. The most common examples are built-up areas, areas under very intensive modern agriculture, and areas with insufficient data quality.

Interpretative mapping is a highly specialised activity carried out with a combination of perception and comprehension. This has two important consequences. Firstly, highly skilled experts in archaeological LiDAR, who are also familiar with the archaeological landscape under investigation, are critical. A vital skill, for example, is the ability to recognise an archaeological feature while filtering out features attributable to modern agricultural practices, geology, and data processing artefacts. Secondly, this process is as subjective as any other archaeological interpretation. Therefore, the level of confidence in each mapped feature will vary, and to maintain scientific integrity, it must be recorded.

(3.3) Ground assessment is a field-based activity that builds upon the interpretative mapping. Its objective is to further decipher, interpret, and understand the archaeological features. Differences in terminology—ground validation, ground-truthing, LiDAR guided survey, and field survey—help to explain the existing differences in the understanding of this activity in archaeological practice. Activities in the field draw heavily from the archaeo-topographical survey, which comprises close observation and interpretation of the ground surface, direct measurement of all significant features, detailed analysis of the relationships between features and the production of a plan that illustrates the arrived at interpretation. In fact, the entire airborne LiDAR workflow is sometimes understood as just an additional method for the archaeo-topographical survey. However, in our view, access to airborne LiDAR data fundamentally redefines the survey by (i) splitting the activities into desk-based interpretative mapping and field-based ground assessment, (ii) enabling unsurpassed metrical accuracy, (iii) providing the widest possible landscape context, and, perhaps most importantly, (iv) enabling precisely targeted and planned fieldwork that can be carried out very efficiently. The latter two are often the key to archaeological interpretation in forests where field-based observation is limited. Therefore, we understand the ground assessment as a LiDAR-specific archaeological method.

The key objectives in the field are to assess features on the ground against the LiDAR-derived information and to search for dating evidence. Landscape study, after all, is desperate for approximate dates that can be provided by small-scale excavation at crucial points or intersections. Valuable secondary information can also be recorded, ranging from learning about the landscape context to interviewing knowledgeable locals. As such, ground assessment is by far the most time-

consuming activity per given area in the entire workflow. Therefore, most often only selected areas and/or features are targeted for ground assessment.

There is an essential aspect of ground assessment that must be carried over from the archaeo-topographical survey if it is to retain its interpretive rigor. This is to understand the undeniable positive effect that a set of bodily practices and sensibilities gained during the field work has on the archaeological interpretation. It stems from “dense, extensive and experiential engagement with its subject landscape that few other archaeological methods could equal”. Since very similar engagement is achieved during the interpretative mapping, ground assessment is at its best when it is intertwined with interpretative mapping in a hermeneutic approach with a feedback loop. In other words, for the best results, personnel involved in interpretative mapping should also be involved in ground assessment and vice versa.

(3.4) The final step in interpretation is the integrated multi-scale ‘deep’ interpretation, which aims to deepen the understanding of the archaeological features in their landscape environment. In a typical application, environmental factors (for example distance to water, soil quality, exposure to wind, visibility) are combined with human agency and individuals by addressing the cognitive space.

(3.5) The automated (or semi-automated) mapping of archaeological features provides a means for rapid data extraction. The two main approaches used today are pixel-based classification and object-oriented image analysis. An emerging trend is the shift from rule-based object detection to machine learning methods. Regardless of the tools used, the method aims to complement interpretative mapping, especially in situations where so much data is available that it becomes difficult to map everything manually.

It is hoped that automated mapping will eventually become a standard part of the workflow, but currently that is not the case. A typical automated mapping project still requires more time and effort than an interpretative mapping, even if the number of targeted features is in the thousands and is therefore undertaken as a separate endeavour. The other main obstacle is that targeted archaeological features not only need to be known, but also need to be very precisely defined in advance (either defined as a rule or “learned” with a machine learning process). Therefore, only archaeological features that have an invariable morphology and are abundant can be targeted. Until now, the focus has been limited to a handful: mound structures (burial mounds, charcoal kilns, and shell rings), pit structures (hunting system; ore extraction pits, and bomb craters), and linear sunken structures (paths, ditches, and mining shafts). There is a recent trend of targeting complex features and multiple feature types (multi-class archaeological object detection), but complex archaeological landscapes embedded in a complex terrain with ample anthropogenic influence remains challenging.

Against this background, the above definition of automated mapping must be adjusted: automated mapping provides a means for rapid mapping of selected categories of previously known archaeological features. In other words, while archaeology is in the process of gaining a powerful mapping tool for known features, archaeological interpretation will remain in the domain of experts for the foreseeable future.

Dissemination and Archiving (4.1–4.3)

The dissemination and archiving of airborne LiDAR data is an important, but until now largely neglected part of the workflow.

(4.1) Since airborne LiDAR datasets are often very large, data management strategies are important. Tiling is an effective way of organising the data during processing and interpretation, as are other standard GIS practices.

(4.2) The dissemination of LiDAR data and, more importantly, its archaeology-specific derivatives received surprisingly little attention in archaeology. Despite the early adoption of webGIS the most ubiquitous form of dissemination remains publication in journals. It is expected that in the near future more suitable forms—fusing the recognition of journal articles with the advantages of webGIS—will prevail.

(4.3) Spatial data archiving issues are currently widely debated inside and outside of archaeology, but as of yet there are no generally accepted practices. The starting premise is that all data, including raw and point-cloud data, should be archived in a persistent repository to make the whole process of processing repeatable. The preparation of LiDAR datasets for archiving requires the choice between different file formats. It has become standard practice in the industry to store data in a compressed open-source LAZ format that complies with ASPRS specification 1.4. Metadata standards for LiDAR data are still evolving and there are no archaeology-specific standards that are widely accepted, but guidance is provided by Opitz (2022). However, archaeologists often do not hold copyright, which can be another problem for archiving. In addition, ethical and regulatory aspects must be considered both in dissemination and archiving. At the very least, however, the results of interpretative mapping should be archived according to accepted standards for GIS data.

Workflow Implementation

The workflow described is not necessarily a linear task that is performed once by a single team. In fact, the opposite is more often the case, and it can also be more productive. An example of good practice is that the raw data acquisition and processing (1.1–1.5) is performed by a team of airborne LiDAR specialists. Another team of archaeologists specialised in airborne LiDAR data will process the point cloud, derive the products (2.1–2.5) and conclude with interpretative mapping (3.1–3.2). Each team will document, disseminate, and archive their respective steps. If off-the-shelf data is used, several years may pass between the two projects. From this point on, different archaeologists may work with the information provided by interpretative mapping, either as part of the daily tasks of heritage management or as part of the teaching process or with a focused research purpose. Other approaches are also possible.

Table 1: Archaeology-specific airborne LiDAR data processing workflow from mission planning to archiving. Arch (aeological) engagement: o nonessential; + as consultant; ++ important; +++ essential.

	Phase	Step	Workflow Step	Arch. Engagement	References
1	Raw data acquisition & Processing	1.1	Project planning	+	[1,2,3]
		1.2	System calibration	o	[1,3,4]
		1.3	Data acquisition	o	[1–7]
		1.4	Registering	+	[1–4,6]
		1.5	Strip adjustment	o	[1–3,6]
2	Point cloud processing	2.1	Automatic ground point classification	++	[1–5,7]
		2.2	Object-type classification	++	[3]

& Derivation of products	2.3	Manual reclassification	+++	[5,6]
	2.4	DFM interpolation	+	[1-3,5,6]
	2.5	Enhanced visualisation	+++	[1-8]
3 Archaeological interpretation	3.1	Data integration	++	[8]
	3.2	Interpretative mapping	+++	[2-5,7,8]
	3.3	Ground assessment	+++	[2,3,5,8]
	3.4	'Deep' interpretation	+++	[2,5]
	3.5	Automated mapping	++	[4]
4 Dissemination & Archiving	4.1	Data management	+	[4,6]
	4.2	Dissemination	+	[2,6]
	4.3	Archiving	+	[2,6]

Table 2: Previously published archaeology-specific airborne LiDAR data processing workflows. Acronyms: d.—data; c.—classification; f.—filtering.

Phase	Step	[27]	[16]	[28]	[13]	[29]	[20]	[21]	[15]
Raw data acquisition & processing	1.1	project planning	project planning			flight planning			project planning
	1.2	system calibration		choice of sensor		system configuration			system calibration
	1.3	data acquisition	d. acquisition	d. acquisition	d. acquisition	d. acquisition	d. collection	d. acquisition	d. acquisition
	1.4	registering	registering	geo-referencing	correlation	d. processing	trajectory determination		geo-referencing
							calibration		
							point cloud production		
	1.5	strip adjustment	grid alignment		strip alignment		project binning		flight strip adjustment
Point cloud processing & Derivation of products	2.1	automatic ground point classification	filtering	filtering	classification (automatic)	d. processing	ground point classification	ground point filtering	classification/ground point filtering
	2.2	object-type classification					object-type point classification		
	2.3	manual reclassification			manual classification			manual classification	
	2.4	DFM interpolation	interpolation		interpolation	d. processing	surface model generation	interpolation	DTM interpolation

2.5	Enhanced visualisation	visualisation	visualisation	visualisation	visualisation	d. visualisation	visualisation	visualisations	visualisation
						quality and accuracy assessment			
						confidence of features			

Phase	Step	[27]	[16]	[28]	[13]	[29]	[20]	[21]	[15]
Archaeological interpretation	3.1	data integration						d. integration	
	3.2	interpretative mapping	mapping	manual detection	interpretative mapping	d. mapping	archaeological interpretation	interpretative mapping	
	3.3	ground assessment	field survey		ground inspection	ground validation		ground-observation	
	3.4	deep' interpretation	additional uses (GIS)		'Deep', integrated multi-scale interpretation				
		automated mapping		automatic detection					
Dissemination & Archiving	4.1	d. management		documentation	d. management				
	4.2	dissemination	dissemination		dissemination				
	4.3	archiving	archiving		archiving				

Data Capture Online Workshop

The Data Capture Online Workshop was held on 22 May 2023. The aim of the workshop was to explore how data capture workflows and the metadata generated through them can be adapted to meet the storytelling needs of different audiences, including multi-disciplinary specialists, creative practitioners, memory institutions and their constituencies.

In attendance were invited speakers and specialists as well as project members from ZRC SAZU, MOLA (Museum of London Archaeology), University of York, University of Antwerp, and Lund University.

In Part 1 there were presentations from different experts working in different contexts with storytelling, LIDAR, 3D scanning, mapping and photography.

In Part 2 we reflected on the relationship between these data capture/structuring processes and storytelling.

Workshop Structure

- Lucija Grahek (ZRC SAZU): From archaeological excavations to storytelling in a museum exhibition, an example from Bela Krajina (Slovenia)
- Elene Leghissa (ZRC SAZU): MOROSTIG: Interpretation of archaeological data for the public.
- Benjamin Štular and Edisa Lozić (TETRARCHS members, ZRC SAZU): Archaeological LiDAR
- Andy Chopping (MOLA): Archaeological Photography at MOLA
- Anna Simandiraki-Grimshaw (MOLA): Attempting to reuse archaeological photos for TETRARCHS.
- Nicolo Dell'Unto (Lund University): 3D Scanning and Image Based Modelling

Lucija Grahek: From archaeological excavations to storytelling in a museum exhibition, an example from Bela Krajina (Slovenia)

Dr. Lucija Grahek, a PhD researcher at ZRC SAZU, shared her experience of bridging the gap between scientific research and public engagement through a project in Bela Krajina, Slovenia. Dr. Grahek explained how she integrated her archaeological excavations and storytelling skills to create a museum exhibition.

Figure 4: Still image from a film created for use within a museum, which was the chosen format for storytelling.

New archaeological discoveries became the catalyst for a much-needed transformation of a nearly half-century-old archaeological exhibition at the Bela Krajina Museum in Metlika. The task of curating a comprehensive and permanent exhibition however, proved to be a major challenge, particularly given its integration within the existing exhibition called “Reflects Across Seven Millennia”. Dr. Grahek emphasised that the entire process was a collaborative effort, requiring teamwork and dedication.

To tackle the project effectively, Dr. Grahek divided the work into three distinct packages: technical design, content creation, and execution. As the main author of the exhibition, she took responsibility for the content. Starting with the preparation of the script, Dr. Grahek outlined three fundamental concepts that guided her throughout the process.

The first concept was completeness, aiming for a comprehensive technical and design layout that accommodated the needs of diverse visitor groups, ranging from preschool children to individuals

with disabilities. Dr. Grahek also sought to achieve chronological and geographical comprehensiveness, ensuring that the exhibition offered a balanced representation of the region's history. The second concept was proportionality, encompassing both geographical and chronological equilibrium in the presentation of various sites and their artefacts. Dr. Grahek strove to strike a balance between scientific expertise and a more accessible presentation, utilising modern technologies and interpretative models alongside the core display of artifacts.

To maintain authenticity, Dr. Grahek decided to focus on one particular archaeological site within the exhibition. This site, one of the most significant in the area, posed a unique challenge due to its vast historical significance within the confined space. Dr. Grahek resolved this issue by opting for a concise animated film, as an alternative to lengthy written explanations on display panels. In the workshop, she presented the film, explaining the process behind its creation and the underlying archaeological data.

Figure 5: The design schema used for storytelling.

The film's script was based on Dr. Grahek's extensive knowledge, gained from scientific publications, her own topographical surveys, and recent excavation projects. Collaborating with professional animators, who initially had no archaeological background, Dr. Grahek provided them with ample visual material to aid their understanding. Similarly, artists responsible for creating illustrations for the text panels received detailed visual references. Dr. Grahek also employed various maps to illustrate the complexity of the site, utilising her own maps based on computer measurements or those derived from scientific publications. Additionally, she incorporated visualisations of leader data and drone footage, meticulously guiding the cameraman to capture specific elements of the site.

Understanding the challenge of comprehending technical aspects for lay visitors, Dr. Grahek sought comparable interpretations in modern research to facilitate their understanding. She also integrated 3D models, generated through photogrammetry or 3D scanning of select objects found during the excavations. Dr. Grahek closely supervised the animator's work, ensuring accuracy and making necessary corrections throughout the process.

Once the basic film was completed, the final step involved preparing and recording the soundtrack, further enhancing the storytelling experience. A key factor in the project's success was effective communication between the content creators and the implementing team. Dr. Grahek acknowledges the positive feedback received from the initial visitors to the Museum, validating the collaborative effort and demonstrating the exhibition's success.

To showcase the project's accomplishments, a film capturing the essence of the exhibition was played.

TETRARCHS team notes on the presentation:

Workflow for creating a short, animated film - centre of presentation:

1. creation of the film script and writing based on own research;
2. develop concept of animated places, objects, finds and illustrations - preparing visual materials, maps to illustrate the complexity of the sites, visualisations of LiDAR data;
3. real time-review and additional corrections;
4. soundtrack preparation and recording;
5. 3D modelling using photogrammetry and 3D scanning;
6. final assembly, review and approval.

Throughout the process there was constant reviewing and checking of the work, alongside a continuous conversation between all stakeholders (experts and creative practitioners).

There was a discussion around how visitors experienced the storytelling movie, with the answer that it acted as guidance for seeing and viewing the objects, allowing visitors to recognise certain themes throughout the exhibition. The focus was primarily on displaying the objects and artefacts, while the digital storytelling acted in complement, helping visitors understand the objects.

Elene Leghissa: MOROSTIG. Interpretation of archaeological data for the public.

Elene Leghissa, PhD, from ZRC SAZU, delivered a presentation on the interpretation of archaeological data for a public audience. The focus of the presentation was a completed project on the biodiversity and heritage of pile dwellings in the Ljubljansko barje, a flood plain located in central Slovenia. This area is renowned for its rich biodiversity and well-preserved remains of a pile dwelling settlement, which is part of the UNESCO heritage as a prehistoric Alpine site.

Figure 6: One of the illustrations created as part of the MOROSTIG project.

The project, officially initiated in 2019 and concluded last year, involved a large team comprised of experts in archaeology, archaeobotany, zoology, geography and botany, along with architects, designers, illustrators, sculptors, and administrative personnel from the municipality. The interdisciplinary nature of the team posed challenges but allowed for a comprehensive implementation of the project's goals.

The project's outcome was the creation of a mock or reconstructed pile dwelling and a path with three key locations. The first location was an interpretation centre in the town of Ig, where visitors learn about botanical, zoological, and archaeological research in the Ljubljansko barje. It also

provides insights into the history and methods used in researching the heritage, the culture of the pile dwellers in Ljubljansko barje, and the measures in place for its international protection.

The aim was to present the content using a combination of classic and modern interpretation methods and tools, distinguishing the centre from a traditional museum. The second location is an automatic trail with stations showcasing the natural heritage's biodiversity and the locations of prehistoric pile dwelling sites. The final stop is a reconstruction of the pile dwelling settlement, offering a glimpse into the daily life of the dwellers during the European Copper Age.

Figure 7: The workflow (on the right) and a critical stage of communication (left), between the interpreter and illustrator in the form of illustration suggestions.

The presentation highlighted a specific example of the process behind creating an illustration for the interpretation centre. To demonstrate the development of building heritage in Ljubljansko barje, the team utilised a timeline on the centre's first floor. The timeline showcased the most important pile dwelling sites and technological advancements across different millennia, incorporating research data such as texts, photos, archaeological plans, and illustrations.

The collaboration between five researchers, including archaeologists, an architect, an archaeobotanist, and an archaeozoologist, was crucial in conceptualising and gathering the required data for the illustrator. The iterative process involved multiple revisions and corrections to ensure the accurate representation of the pile dwelling settlement. Challenges arose in reconciling the diverse requirements of individual researchers, necessitating compromises and the intervention of an interpreter or mediator between the researchers and the illustrator.

The presentation emphasised the importance of clear communication and effective storytelling to facilitate understanding and successfully convey complex data to the illustrator. It was noted that

popular texts, in addition to scientific publications, proved helpful in conveying the desired information effectively. Elene Leghissa, an archaeologist and interpreter, played a vital role in processing and conveying key information to the illustrator, ensuring the project's successful completion.

In conclusion, the project exemplified the process of interpreting archaeological data for a public audience. Through a collaborative effort involving experts from various fields, the team created an interpretation centre, an automatic trail, and a reconstruction of a pile dwelling settlement. The challenges faced in conveying information to the illustrator highlighted the importance of effective communication and the role of interpreters in bridging the gap between researchers and visual representation. Overall, the project successfully showcased the rich cultural and natural heritage of the Ljubljansko barje to the public.

TETRARCHS team notes on the presentation:

A large team was involved across the duration of the projects: an archaeologist, an archaeozoologist, an archaeobotanist, palynologists, geographers, architects, designers, illustrators, sculptors, botanists. There were also two interpreters involved (nature heritage - culture heritage).

Results of the project: Morostig - House of nature and pile dwellings in the Ljubljansko barje were:

1. a new interpretation centre: providing information about the first botanical, zoological and archaeological research in the Ljubljansko barje, the history and methods of researching this heritage over time, an overview of the culture of pile dwellers, biodiversity and international protection measures;
2. combining of classical and more modern techniques;
3. a thematic trail highlighting natural heritage and locations of prehistoric pile-dwelling sites;
4. a reconstruction of the pile-dwelling settlements;
5. original finds – combined with palaeoenvironmental data.

It would be useful to see the full workflow, from idea > selection of content > focus of the content > info sent to illustrator > first illustration proposals > revisions and corrections (multiple times) > final and to see what the 'content' actually look like in terms of data points.

This represents an interesting example of storytelling = illustration (in the previous examples, storytelling = film). Discussion of whether the traditional museum display of objects in glass cases is or is not considered storytelling.

Both this and the previous example make a distinction between the museum and the act of storytelling. This raises the issue of what level of interpretation -> makes it storytelling - and what these levels of interpretation are.

Discussion of the two examples presented by the two invited speakers highlighting the fact that while they were operating on very different budgets (the second being 1000x higher than the first) the workflows were comparable. This was viewed as positive from the TETRARCHS viewpoint, because it allows a "general" workflow to be mapped in both instances.

Benjamin Štular and Edisa Lozić: Archaeological LiDAR

The presentation by Benjamin Štular and Edisa Lozić introduced the data capture workflow for archaeological LiDAR (Light Detection and Ranging). LiDAR is an airborne laser scanning technique used to create enhanced visualisations of the ground, revealing archaeological features. The presenters highlighted the importance of this technology in the field of archaeology and provided an overview of the workflow. The workflow is divided into four major blocks: raw data acquisition and processing, point cloud processing and derivation of products, archaeological interpretation, and dissemination and archiving.

Raw data acquisition and processing consists of project planning, system calibration, data acquisition, registering, and strip adjustments. While some steps are typically handled by specialists in laser scanning, archaeologists are increasingly utilising their own drone-based LiDAR systems. Project planning and data acquisition require archaeologists to determine the type of features they are interested in, considering the trade-off between area coverage and data quality.

In point cloud processing and derivation of products, archaeologists engage in five steps. The first step is automatic ground point classification, which is a crucial part of the data processing stage. Object type classification follows, which includes identifying various features such as buildings, vegetation, and infrastructure. Manual classification becomes necessary in unfavourable conditions or within areas of high interest. DFM interpolation, an often-overlooked step, is essential for generating the digital feature model (archaeological DEM) that includes the ground, modern buildings, and archaeological elements. Enhanced visualisation, a popular aspect among archaeologists, maximizes the impact of the data.

Archaeological interpretation involves data integration, interpretative mapping, automatic mapping (optional), ground assessment, and deep interpretation. Data integration brings together various data sources, such as aerial photography, historic maps, geology, and archaeology, in a GIS environment. Interpretative mapping involves vectorising archaeological features based on the operator's interpretation. Automatic mapping using deep learning techniques may also be employed. Ground assessment, including field work and trenching, is essential for validation. Deep interpretation considers the interpreted mapping and ground assessment as part of a broader archaeological interpretation, involving spatial analysis and statistics.

Interpretative mapping, considered a critical step, entails the identification, interpretation, and mapping of archaeological sites and features based on LiDAR-derived data. The aim is to create a geodatabase with feature-specific metadata, although metadata usage in archaeology is not yet widespread. This step involves subjective interpretation, and confidence levels and other metadata are recorded to acknowledge this subjectivity.

Finally, dissemination and archiving, emphasises the importance of data management, dissemination, and archiving. Following good practice in GIS and ensuring proper metadata collection, recording, and archiving are crucial for LiDAR-specific data management. The presenters advocated for the inclusion of metadata in any type of dissemination to improve transparency and reproducibility.

Figure 8. Data capture and processing workflow for archaeological LiDAR.

In conclusion, the presentation provided an overview of the archaeological LiDAR data capture workflow, covering raw data acquisition, point cloud processing, archaeological interpretation, and dissemination/archiving. It emphasised the importance of understanding the subjective nature of the process and the significance of proper data management and metadata in ensuring accurate and transparent archaeological research.

Andy Chopping and Anna Simandiraki-Grimshaw: Archaeological Photography at MOLA

Andy Chopping, a photographer at MOLA (Museum of London Archaeology), discussed the process of archaeological photography and its integration into a searchable database. The presentation began with the importance of selecting appropriate photographs for archival purposes and embedding them in the database. Chopping provided an example from his recent photography session at Lambeth Palace, the London home of the Archbishop of Canterbury.

The process involves the photographer visiting the site and receiving instructions from field archaeologists regarding what they intend to document. In addition to capturing the requested images, they also capture any visually significant details that contribute to the story. The images are initially recorded in a RAW format, similar to traditional celluloid negatives, and then processed using software like Photoshop. The processed images are then loaded into the searchable database with basic information provided by the photographer.

Over time, field archaeologists enhance the information associated with the images using their own records. This additional data, such as context information and broader descriptions, enables more comprehensive searches in the future. Users can search the database using various criteria, including the date of capture or image description. Chopping shared an example where a colleague requested images depicting cattle bones, and he was able to find suitable images by searching for "horn core pit."

1044	W	FIRM BLACK STERILE DEPOSIT (4124)	0.5	LJ	21
1050	W	" "	"	"	"
1051	S	" "	"	"	"
1052	W	" "	"	"	"
1053	/	TAGS IN BACK (NEXT PHASE)	/	FR	"
1054	/	" " "	/	FR	"
1055	N	(4128) OVER COBBLES	0.5m	SM%	22/01/2020
1056	N	" " "	/	"	"
1057	N	" " "	0.5m	"	"
1058	S	" " "	0.5m	"	"
1059	S	" " "	/	"	"
1060	N	ROBBEY CUT (4131)*	1m	LJ	23/01/2020
1061	W	ROBBEY CUT (4131) + WALL FOUNDATION (4127)	"	"	"
1062	W	" "	/	"	"
1063	E	" "	1m	"	"
1064	N	ROBBEY CUT (4131), MASONRY (4120), FOUNDATION (4127)	/	"	"
1065	N	" "	/	"	"
1066	N	COBBLES (4132) WITH N/S MASONRY			
1067	N	" " "	0.5	SM%	24/01/2020
1068	N	" " "	"	"	"
1069	N	" " "	"	"	"

Figure 9: Field recordings are the starting point of metadata creation for archaeological photography.

Chopping explained that the database used to display thumbnail images for easier browsing, but due to technical issues and online security concerns, this feature is currently unavailable. He demonstrated a search for a specific object, emphasising the importance of adding defining features like register finds numbers to narrow down the results. Studio photography follows a similar process, where photographers are briefed on specific artefacts and create images with a legible scale for the database.

A noteworthy difference in studio photography is the inclusion of metadata within the digital photographs themselves. This ensures that important information remains accessible even when the photographs are separated from the database. Chopping expresses concern about the current limitations of the database, as it prevents external users from viewing the images they need, citing an example where a poor photograph was used instead of a better alternative.

The presentation highlights the traditional method of recording and archiving images, primarily captured with DSLR-style cameras, and the ongoing trial of a system called the Apex Recording System. This system allows immediate uploading of images to a cloud-based searchable database, linked to specific contexts and sites. However, the current image size limitation of two megabytes hinders its effectiveness for publication purposes. Chopping mentions that some archaeologists also contribute photographs taken with DSLR cameras on-site, which undergo processing and are uploaded to the database later. Unfortunately, the issue of images not being visible persists with these records as well. Chopping concludes the presentation by acknowledging Anna Simandiraki-Grimshaw's contribution to image selection and the utilisation of metadata.

Figure 10: A screenshot of the network-based relational database that is the backbone of the photography metadata database at MOLA.

In summary, the presentation provided an overview of archaeological photography at MOLA, discussing the process of capturing, archiving, and incorporating images into a searchable database. It emphasises the importance of thorough documentation and the challenges faced in accessing and utilising the images effectively.

Anna Simandiraki-Grimshaw then presented her work with Sara Perry attempting to reuse archaeological photos for TETRARCHS.

With guidance from Sara and discussions with Andy, they selected a sample of 50 photos with various characteristics, such as people, stratigraphy, and context. Along with the photographs, they received metadata that had been detached from the database.

Anna focused on a particular photo of a shoe, considering it evocative and representative of the material. She entered the metadata into an Excel sheet and received additional information from colleagues who had worked with the artifacts in the photos. They cross-referenced different sources to determine the artifact's accession number and incorporated all relevant data into the Excel sheet.

One challenge the team faced was the lack of information about the publication status of the photos in the database. Anna had to search through external sources and consult with Andy to gather the necessary details. This collaborative effort allowed them to obtain as comprehensive a set of metadata as possible for the photos.

The reuse workflow involved several steps. First, they identified the desired samples and cross-referenced the data. Next, they collated and merged information from different sources, ensuring that overlapping data were combined. Their objective was to reuse the photos for creative purposes and storytelling.

Figure 11: A reuse journey of an archaeological photograph of a shoe at MOLA.

Anna and Sara conducted a pre-workshop workshop with their colleagues from MOLA, where new metadata were created for the artefacts without most participants having prior knowledge of existing metadata. This process involved decontextualising the artefacts from their archaeological and database context, generating fresh metadata, and retagging the photos.

In conclusion, Anna presented an overview of the reuse journey, highlighting the importance of collaboration, collation of information, and the generation of new metadata.

TETRACH's team notes on the MOLA presentations:

The workflow for images at MOLA includes: a RAW digital image - processed in photoshop - uploaded in searchable databases. Image registers are made on site and extra data is added to the searchable database.

If the end user that wants to find an image they can navigate and filter on various fields.

Discussion of the use of living memory is a regular feature of how people 'search' for things at MOLA, and online security as a reason why the IT department cannot permit searching via the images themselves.

Further discussions of the 'Meta-life' of the photo, and understanding the motivations for reuse.

Nicolo Dell'Unto: 3D Scanning and Image Based Modelling

Nicolo Dell'Unto delved into the world of 3D scanning and image-based modelling and their impact on archaeological data analysis. Dell'Unto shared his perspective on the use of these technologies in the field and explored how they have transformed our perception and understanding of the past. The presentation was divided into three key steps that shed light on the potential and challenges of utilising visualisation technology in archaeology.

Dell'Unto discussed the influence of visualisation technology on perception. Over the past two decades, he has actively engaged in 3D data recording and analysis, encountering various types of datasets that struggled to find their place in the field. He emphasised that 3D data in archaeology can be broadly classified into 'phase boundary' and 'volume representation', each with its unique characteristics and requirements.

What does it look like to gather the data (i.e., what is your 'data capturing journey' with your respective medium)?

Dell'Unto, N., & Landeschi, G. (2022). *Archaeological 3D GIS*. Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003034131>

Figure 12: Images of archaeological 3D data capture in the field.

Addressing scepticism and criticism surrounding the use of 3D technology, Dell'Unto highlighted the evolving landscape of archaeological practice. Rather than taking a definitive stance on its adoption, he emphasised the importance of engaging in ongoing discussions. Contrary to the belief that technology enhances efficiency and objectivity, Dell'Unto argued that it has introduced additional complexity to archaeology, but he finds this complexity more engaging and believes that 3D visualisation opens up new avenues for practice and theory development.

The process of data acquisition typically involves image-based modelling techniques in the field, as they offer flexibility and excellent results. Dell'Unto described the progression from data acquisition to the generation of various models such as sparse dense clouds, mesh models, and texture models. These models serve as references imported into GIS or 3D GIS for generating graphic documentation and metadata description. He emphasised how digital technology disrupts traditional field practices, revolutionising the way we perceive, record, and share archaeological data.

Moreover, Dell'Unto underscored the transformative nature of machine-readable, easily discoverable, and reusable data, capable of supporting multiple narratives and their integration into different contexts. He acknowledged this phenomenon evokes mixed emotions, with frustration over losing control of traditional storytelling and the potential for decolonising archaeological practices.

How, where and when are the data described and structured?

Label	Class	Owner
3D media	Interactive Resource	Paola Tharros
3D model	D1_Digital_Object	Paola Tharros
3DHOP Scene	S9_Property_Type	Paola Tharros
Context (clay structure)	A8_Stratigraphic_Unit	Paola Tharros
Context (cut)	A3_Stratigraphic_Interface	Paola Tharros
Context (default)	A8_Stratigraphic_Unit	Paola Tharros
Context (fill/layer)	A8_Stratigraphic_Unit	Paola Tharros
Context (skeleton)	A8_Stratigraphic_Unit	Paola Tharros
Context (stone structure)	A8_Stratigraphic_Unit	Paola Tharros
Context (timber structure)	A8_Stratigraphic_Unit	Paola Tharros
Dynamic Collections	D1_Digital_Object	Paola Tharros
Excavation unit	A8_Stratigraphic_Unit	Paola Tharros
Feature	A6_Group_Declaration_Event	Paola Tharros
Field Survey Unit	SP6_Declarative_Place	Paola Tharros
Find	Physical Thing	Paola Tharros
GIS data	D1_Digital_Object	Paola Tharros
Group	A6_Group_Declaration_Event	Paola Tharros
Investigation area	A1_Excavation_Process_Unit	Paola Tharros
Investigation campaign	A9_Archaeological_Excavation	Paola Tharros
Paragraph	document part	Paola Tharros
Person	Person	Paola Tharros
Report	Document	Paola Tharros
Sample	S13_Sample	Paola Tharros

Figure 13: A screenshot of 3D metadata within an Omeka-based data management system used at Lund University.

Dell'Unto then explores the description and organisation of data and how they shape knowledge production. Data description extends beyond the initial collection phase and evolves throughout the research project. The interpretive nature of records requires flexibility in modifying descriptions, and the digital realm provides a manipulable and organised space for this purpose. He introduced an ongoing Web 3D archive project that enables immediate importation of field data, accompanied by metadata descriptions, enhancing accessibility and reuse possibilities.

While accessing and reusing data in digital archives may not be straightforward, Dell'Unto highlighted the importance of studying how people engage with and customise these systems. He emphasises the need for reflection, experimentation, and observation to maximise the potential of data reuse in the digital world.

Dell'Unto shared insights from the Dynamic Collections Project, focusing on innovative ways of engaging with archaeological material online and promoting knowledge generation and data reuse. By incorporating diverse perspectives and fostering the sharing of narratives, the project transcends a purely measurement-driven approach. The challenges of using these tools for educational purposes, especially bridging the generation gap, were also discussed.

In conclusion, Dell'Unto emphasized that 3D scanning and image-based modelling have revolutionised archaeological data analysis. These technologies provide new possibilities for understanding the past, but also necessitate continuous exploration, adaptation, and reflection. By embracing the potential of digital archives and creating user-friendly systems, archaeology can unlock vast opportunities for knowledge production and engagement.

TETRARCHS team notes on the presentation:

Discussion about the need to study how people re-use data, experiment more with how to optimise digital environments to improve the reuse, evaluate what it looks like for other people to access and reuse the data, and examine how people interact with the environment.

Panel Discussion

The panel was moderated by Piraye Hacigüzeller and Aida Fadioui, and the panel participants included Lucija Grahek, Benjamin Štular, Edisa Lozić, Andy Chopping, Nicolo Dell'Unto, Sara Perry, Stuart Eve, James Ladocha, Adam Sutton, Lise Foket, Hélène Verreyke.

The aim of the panel discussion was to reflect on how archaeological data creators envisage different audiences using the datasets they generate, and how metadata are created and located in different archaeological data workflows.

To achieve this, a series of questions were designed to get panelists thinking about metadata generation and management, reuse by different audiences, storytelling techniques, and data collection workflows. We wanted to know how people envisioned the “reuse journeys” for the data they generated.

The discussion was recorded then transcribed and annotated.

Themes: metadata generation point, alternative recording tools and strategies, analogue methods complementing digital methods, co-creation, data reuse by data creators, natural language and structured data.

The first part of the discussion revolved around tools to generate and manage metadata. For some participants most of the tools and software they use haven't changed much over time, as they still work similarly. These include searchable databases, spreadsheets, and software such as ArcGIS, OmekaS, but also analogue tools such as notebooks.

For one panelist there was a feeling of being overwhelmed by the rapidly changing technologies if they tried to keep up with everything in the archaeological field. This raised the question of the division of labour in a team of people with different skillsets and the necessity of communication and collaboration within said team and beyond. The question of when we should be generating metadata was raised (and was an important theme during the rest of the discussion).

The next theme was related to structured and unstructured data, with panelists remarking that even when a free text box was available it would often comprise information already available elsewhere under a different category. There seems to be a need for some sort of prompt to encourage people to be more playful and not restricted by the same parameters that exist outside of free text, which in turn would support diverse interpretations of the record.

The next question was about audiences, which led to a discussion about the idea that specialists are sometimes the first audience to reuse their own data. The panelists work with, and for, a variety of audiences, whether it's other specialists or the larger audience of a cultural institution, work needs to be done to make this data accessible to them and vice-versa, but this will oftentimes put restraints on the formats that can be used and what exactly is recorded. There are added challenges when collaborating with different stakeholders on a project where everyone has different expectations and a different process, specific to their institution or background.

There was also the question of community involvement in research projects, and how that could impact research questions but also how the lack of involvement usually means the archaeological record is not accessible to non-specialists. Metadata generation in the field was then discussed, as it is usually created and discussed and revisited – and thus reused. But in some cases, metadata generation comes later in the process, at the point of archiving, completely divorcing it from its context. There was also a concern about non-traditional recording strategies such as video diaries, which can't be classified in the same way and thus are harder to access.

Finally, panelists quickly discussed the impact of working on exhibitions or community projects using storytelling based on archaeological work from their own practices, and how they became more mindful in their processes working with different stakeholders.

Unfortunately, there was only time to go through a few of the prepared questions, but the panel discussion was very useful, and many themes were raised. The topic of when metadata should be created appears to be important to most panelists, who all agree it should be an inherent part of the data capture workflow, and while digital tools are widely used, analogue tools haven't disappeared yet and feel like they are complementary, as they offer a certain ease on the field as well as an opportunity to record unstructured data in a more playful and creative way.

The place of natural language – or unstructured data in general – was also an important theme in the conversation, with discussions on the restraining character intrinsic to most recording formats.

It was also noted that while metadata is an integral part of every project, the technical knowledge needed can be overwhelming, as it needs further specialisation which might not be a priority for all practitioners. Tools should be more accessible, and knowledge of technical aspects more common, but projects should involve an interdisciplinary team with a variety of skillsets.

In future panel discussions and interviews, TETRARCHS will be focusing more on reuse journeys for practitioners and different audiences. The questions will be tailored to our audiences, and we hope to organise another discussion with specialists involving the MOLA team as well as with creative practitioners in the future.

Conclusion

This deliverable has outlined the range of experimental workflows developed by TETRARCHS partners within the first six months on the project. Most of these experiments will be implemented over the next six months as part of Task 5.2: *Experiment Design Implementation*. This will allow reflection and time for iterative improvements in the second year, (as appropriate) within Task 5.3: *Updates to Experiment Design Implementation*. Both the initial and updated implementation results will be reported iteratively in project Months M15, M24, M33, within Deliverable 5.2: *Experiment Trials*.

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TETRARCHs is making archaeological data accessible to a wider range of people.

The project explores how data from excavations and post-excavation research can be used and reused for educational, creative, and other life-enriching purposes. We work collaboratively across a variety of communities to experiment with storytelling about the past.

- **For heritage professionals, we create new resources for developing and measuring the effectiveness of archaeological data for storytelling.**
- **For memory institutions like museums and cultural centres, we create reference materials to support you using these new resources for storytelling.**
- **For creatives and local citizens, we will create a platform where you can search for and experiment with storytelling about the past.**

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